

Synthesis, characterization and reactivity of dichloro bis(4-methoxyphenoxo)tin(IV)

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Abstract : The dichloro bis(4-methoxyphenoxo)tin(IV) complex of composition $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ has been synthesized in quantitative yield by the reaction of tin tetrachloride with bimolar amount of 4-methoxyphenol in benzene under reflux and characterized by elemental analyses, molar conductance measurement, molecular weight determination, IR, ^1H NMR and FAB-mass spectral techniques. The thermal behaviour of the complex has been studied by TG-DTA techniques. The reactions of parent complex with nitrogenous bases viz. diethylamine, triethylamine, imidazole, benzimidazole (L), 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline (B) yielded addition compounds of composition $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2\cdot 2\text{L}$ and $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2\cdot \text{B}$ characterized by physicochemical and IR spectral data.

Keywords : Tin(IV) complex, 4-methoxyphenol, spectroscopic studies, nitrogenous bases, addition compounds, FAB-mass.

Introduction

Survey of literature reveals that bulk of the research over the years has been directed towards the synthesis of transition metal and lanthanide complexes of substituted phenols while that of main group analogues has comparatively been quite less explored¹⁻⁶, although there is a considerable scope for systematic investigation on the synthesis and biochemical applications of the complexes of non-transition elements particularly that of tin with biologically active ligands⁷⁻¹⁰. The potential role played by such ligand complexes of tin(II) and tin(IV) has been demonstrated by Gielen and co-workers¹¹ in pre-clinical screening of new antitumour agents. The electronic structure of newly synthesized tin anticancer complexes coordinating one, two and four tin atoms has been investigated by Chojnacki¹² while thermochemistry of adducts of tin(IV) chloride with heterocyclic bases has been reported by Dunsan¹³. Tin complexes of modified porphyrins such as purpurins have been studied as photodynamic therapy drugs and are known to show good efficacy *in vitro*¹⁴ while tin(IV) protoporphyrins are reported to be an inhibitor of haemoxygenase, a possible agent for the treatment of neonatal jaundice¹⁵. Apart from this a number of tin(II) and tin(IV) aryloxides have been characterized as mono and binuclear on the basis of steric

bulk of the ring substituents¹⁶. Chiral tin(IV) aryloxides prepared from binol derivatives and SnCl_4 have been reported to catalyze Diel's-Alder reaction of α,β -unsaturated aldehydes with cyclopentadiene to give cyclo adducts with high enantio-selectivity¹⁷. Encouraged by these reports on inorganic tin complexes, it is worthwhile to undertake the synthesis of a new complex dichloro bis(4-methoxyphenoxo)tin(IV) and investigate its physico-chemical properties including reactivity with some nitrogenous bases.

Results and discussion

The formation of the title compound has been rationalized in terms of the following reaction :

The stoichiometric composition of the solid compound isolated from the solution has been established by elemental analysis (Found : Sn, 26.98; Cl, 16.02; C, 38.29; H, 3.11. Calcd : Sn, 27.29; Cl, 16.28; C, 38.53; H, 3.21%). The compound is a light yellow solid and quite stable in dry conditions. It is soluble in organic polar solvents viz. nitrobenzene, nitromethane, acetonitrile etc. The molar conductance value of millimolar solution of this compound in nitrobenzene is $0.86 \text{ S cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$ suggesting its non-electrolytic nature in this sol-

vent. Molecular weight determination of this compound by Rast's camphor method indicates this compound to be monomer. Further information on the structure and nature of this compound has been obtained by IR, NMR, Mass spectra and TG-DTA studies.

IR spectra :

The infrared spectrum of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ recorded in $4000\text{--}250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region revealed that broad band observed in $3350\text{--}3250\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region due to hydrogen bonded phenolic OH group^{18,19} in free 4-methoxyphenol is missing while the bands in $1600\text{--}1400\text{ cm}^{-1}$ region attributed to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ in phenolic ring have been found to shift slightly towards higher wave numbers possibly due to increased ring conjugation brought about by complex formation. The most important and diagnostic band due to $\nu_{\text{ring}}\text{CO}$ mode reported to oc-

cur around 1265 cm^{-1} in pure 4-methoxyphenol appeared at 1215 cm^{-1} in the complex. This significant lowering by about 50 cm^{-1} has been rationalized in terms of bonding from phenolic oxygen to tin which is also substantiated by the appearance of entirely new band in $600\text{--}550\text{ cm}^{-1}$ (not present in the ligand) attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn-O})$ modes^{20,21}. Further the bands in the range $335\text{--}350\text{ cm}^{-1}$ may be attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn-Cl})$ stretching modes.

NMR spectra :

The ^1H NMR spectrum of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ did not display any signal at $\delta 4.9\text{ ppm}$ due to phenolic OH group in pure 4-methoxyphenol, suggesting thereby the deprotonation and formation of the resulting complex. The aromatic ring protons resonance at $\delta 6.62\text{ ppm}$ in uncoordinated phenol have been observed to undergo

Scheme 1. Fragmentation pattern of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$.

Table 1 Analytical data of adducts of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ with nitrogenous bases

Complex	Colour	M p (°C)	Elemental analysis (%)				Molar conductance ($\text{S cm}^2 \text{ mol}^{-1}$)		
			Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)	Found (Calcd)			
			Sn	Cl	C	H	N	Molecular weight	
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_2\text{NH}$	Cream	180	20.02 (20.42)	11.99 (12.18)	45.02 (45.31)	6.02 (6.17)	4.74 (4.80)	598 (582.56)	2.3
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot 2\text{Et}_3\text{N}$	White	156	18.12 (18.64)	10.92 (11.12)	48.38 (48.88)	6.72 (6.89)	4.28 (4.38)	654 (638.28)	1.6
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot 2\text{Imid}$	Cream	158	20.21 (20.78)	12.12 (12.40)	41.58 (41.92)	3.71 (3.84)	9.69 (9.78)	586 (572.44)	2.5
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot 2\text{Benzimid}$	White	140	17.30 (17.69)	10.02 (10.55)	49.62 (49.95)	3.78 (3.86)	8.26 (8.32)	687 (672.56)	2.2
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot \text{Bipy}$	Pink	184(d)	19.98 (20.08)	11.32 (11.98)	48.42 (48.61)	3.41 (3.71)	4.61 (4.72)	-	2.1
$\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot \text{Phen}$	Pink	190(d)	18.28 (19.30)	11.21 (11.51)	50.34 (50.60)	3.42 (3.56)	4.32 (4.54)	-	1.7

d = Decomposition point

Fig. 1. Thermoanalytical curves of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$.

a significant downfield shift and appeared at δ 6.76 ppm while the signal at δ 3.70 ppm due to methoxy protons remained almost unaltered even on complex formation. The observed downfield shift of the phenyl ring proton resonances may be rationalized in terms of deshielding of these protons due to drainage of electron density from the aromatic ring to tin metal, which is in agreement with the earlier report of Clark and coworkers²². The integration of signals due to phenyl and methoxy protons supported the stoichiometric formulation of the complex.

Mass spectra :

The formation of the compound of composition $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ has further been ascertained by the appearance of an intense peak at m/e 410 (22%) attributed to $[\text{M-C}_2\text{H}_2]^+$ in FAB mass spectrum. The molecular ion peak $[\text{M}]^+$ expected at m/e 436 appears to have disintegrated during fragmentation because of its unstable nature. Other important peaks observed at m/e 338 (72%), 313 (22.22%), 281 (33%), 241 (17%), 207 (30%), 191 (28%), 154 (100%), 123 (36%), 107 (66%) and 95 (75%) may be rationalized in terms of various fragments formed during successive removal of different groups is shown in Scheme 1.

Apart from the molecular ion peaks in the above pattern, the significant mass ion peaks at 367 (31%) and 327 (39%) have been attributed to the formation of fragments $\text{H}_2\text{Sn}(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ and $\text{SnOCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{CHO})$ respectively.

Based upon above physico-chemical and spectral data, a tetrahedral structure can be assigned to the parent compound $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$.

Thermal studies :

Thermal behaviour of the complex has been investigated by TG-DTA technique in air (Fig. 1). A perusal of the TG curve of the complex showed it to be thermally quite stable as is indicated by initial decomposition temperature at about 120 °C. The complex undergoes single stage decomposition as is substantiated by the DTG curve, showing maximum rate of decomposition of 35.12% per minute at 175.44 °C. The weight loss of 69.61% accompanied by endothermic peak in DTA curve at 174.12 °C corresponds well with the formation of SnO as ultimate residue and thereby also confirming the stoichiometric formulation of the complex. Based on the weight loss, following decomposition step has been proposed

Reactions of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ with nitrogenous bases :

Reactivity of the newly synthesized $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ has been investigated by undertaking its reactions with various nitrogenous bases such as diethylamine, triethylamine, imidazole (imid), benzimidazole (benzimid), 1,10-phenanthroline (phen) and 2,2'-bipyridyl (bipy). The interaction of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ with diethylamine, triethylamine, imidazole and benzimidazole in 1 : 2 molar ratio afforded the formation of adducts of composition $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot 2\text{L}$, while with bidentate 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl in equimolar ratios resulted in the formation of adducts of composition $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2 \cdot \text{B}$. Stoichiometric composition of these addition compounds has been established by elemental analysis (Table 1). The molar conductance values of millimolar solution of these adducts in nitrobenzene are too low to be attributed as electrolytes. Molecular weight determination of some of these adducts by Rast camphor method suggests that they exist as monomers.

Further evidences for the formation of these adducts has been obtained from their IR spectra. The significant lowering of about 40–50 cm^{-1} in $\nu(\text{NH})$ mode observed in 3300–3400 cm^{-1} region in pure amines has been attributed to the weakening of NH bond presumably due to donation of the electrons from nitrogen to tin. This is further supported by lowering of $\nu(\text{CN})$ modes of Et_2NH and Et_3N observed in 1170–1190 and 1030–1230 cm^{-1} respectively by about 50–60 cm^{-1} in its adducts with $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$. These trends of shift in the $\nu(\text{NH})$, $\nu(\text{CN})$ and HNC deformation modes are in agreement with the earlier reports on the adducts of these amines with various transition metal halides²³. Similarly the absorption bands observed at 3206 and 3117 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{NH})$ modes in uncoordinated imidazole and benzimidazole respectively²⁴ appear around 3190 and 3108 cm^{-1} . The bands in the range 1620–1450 cm^{-1} in free bases due to $\nu(\text{C}=\text{C})$ and $(\text{C}=\text{N})$ mode²⁵ have been found to shift towards higher frequencies viz. 1660–1410 cm^{-1} in the adducts. The observed trend of shifts²⁶ suggested that these bases are monodentately coordinated through nitrogen

to tin metal, which is in agreement with the earlier reports²⁷.

In case of addition compounds with 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline, coordination from both the nitrogen atom of these ligands has been indicated by the positive shift in $\text{C}=\text{C}$ and $\text{C}=\text{N}$ ring stretching vibration of the uncoordinated bases²⁸ known to occur in the region 1590–1560 cm^{-1} by about 15–20 cm^{-1} . The C–H out of plane deformation mode around 759 cm^{-1} in case of 2,2'-bipyridyl has been found to split into two bands and is observed as a weak band around 768 cm^{-1} upon adduct formation. In case of 1,10-phenanthroline, however the (C–H) out of plane deformation vibration observed at 852 and 837 cm^{-1} in uncoordinated base, appear to have moved to higher spectral region on adduct formation by about 15–20 cm^{-1} suggesting coordination from both the nitrogen atoms of the ligand, which is in agreement with the earlier reports on 2,2'-bipyridyl and 1,10-phenanthroline adducts with metal halides²⁹. The coordination of the bases to tin in all the adducts has further been substantiated by the appearance of entirely new bands in the far IR region 390–420 cm^{-1} attributed to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{N})$ stretching modes³⁰. It is pertinent to mention here that there is no splitting of bands due to $\nu(\text{Sn}-\text{Cl})$ even on adduct formation and sharp bands in the range 330–350 cm^{-1} have been observed³¹.

Based upon the analytical and IR spectral data on the addition compounds isolated in the present studies, an octahedral structure may be assigned for adducts with two chlorine atoms *trans* to each other.

Experimental

4-Methoxyphenol (Merck, m.p. 54 °C) was recrystallised from benzene before use. Anhydrous SnCl_4 (A.R.) was distilled under reduced pressure. The nitrogenous bases used in the present study were of A.R. grade and used as such without further purification.

Tin content in complexes was determined as SnO_2 after decomposing the complex with a mixture of concentrated H_2SO_4 and HNO_3 followed by heating to 600–700 °C. Chlorine was determined by Volhard's method. Molecular weights of the complexes were determined by Rast camphor method. Molar conductance measurements were made in nitrobenzene on Elico-conducti-

vity bridge. CM type 82T. Micro analyses for carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen were performed on Coleman C H N analyzer. The IR spectra were recorded (as KBr pellets and as nujol mull on CsI optics) on Nicolet-5700 FTIR spectrometer. The ^1H NMR spectrum was recorded on Bruker-AC 300 MHz spectrometer using TMS as internal standard and CDCl_3 as solvent. The FAB mass spectrum was recorded on JEOL SX-102 DA-6000 mass spectrometer using Ar/Xe as the FAB gas. Thermogram was recorded on a simultaneous DT-TG Shimadzu thermal analyzer DT-60.

Preparation of complexes :

To a solution of SnCl_4 (1.5 g, 5.7 mM) in dry benzene (30 mL), bimolar amount of 4-methoxyphenol (1.43 g, 11.4 mM) dissolved separately in the same solvent was added slowly. The reaction mixture was refluxed for about 30–35 h till there was no evolution of hydrogen chloride gas. The resulting solution was then concentrated by distilling off most of the solvent and left overnight. A light yellow solid appeared in the solution, separated by filtration, washed repeatedly with petroleum ether and finally dried under vacuum.

Preparation of addition compounds of $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ with nitrogenous bases :

A known amount of parent compound $\text{SnCl}_2(\text{OC}_6\text{H}_4\text{OMe-4})_2$ in THF/MeOH solvent was reacted directly with equimolar amounts of 1,10-phenanthroline and 2,2'-bipyridyl and bimolar amounts of diethylamine, triethylamine, imidazole and benzimidazole under continuous stirring. A slight change in the colour of the solution was observed. The reaction mixture was stirred for about 12 h followed by slight warming to ensure the completion of the reaction. The were then concentrated by evaporating the solvent under vacuum. The solid adducts were then isolated either by the addition of petroleum ether or by leaving the solution overnight. These adducts were separated by filtration, washed several times with petroleum ether and finally dried in vacuum.

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References

1. D. C. Bradley, R. C. Mehrotra, I. P. Rothwell and A. Singh, "Alkoxo and Aryloxo Derivative of Metals", Academic Press, London, 2001, 445.
2. K. C. Malhotra and R. L. Martin, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1982, **239**, 159.
3. A. E. Fenwick, K. Phomphrai, M. G. Thorn, J. S. Vilaro, C. A. Trefun, B. Hanna, P. E. Fanwick and I. P. Rothwell, *Organometallics*, 2004, **23**, 2146.
4. M. Y. Deng, Y. M. Yao, Q. Shen, Y. Zhang and J. Sun, *J. Chem. Soc., Dalton Trans.*, 2004, 944.
5. Y. M. Yao, Q. Shen and J. Sun, *Polyhedron*, 1998, **17**, 519.
6. Y. M. Yao, Q. Shen, Y. Zhang, M. Q. Xue and J. Sun, *Polyhedron*, 2001, **20**, 3201.
7. H. D. Yin and S. W. Chem, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 2006, **359**, 3330; *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 2006, **691**, 3103.
8. M. A. Ali, A. H. Mirza, M. Haneti, S. A. Hamid and P. V. Bernhardt, *Polyhedron*, 2005, **24**, 383.
9. T. M. Aminabhavi, N. S. Biradar, S. B. Patil, V. L. Radhabasangoudar and W. E. Rudzinski, *Inorg. Chim. Acta*, 1985, **107**, 231.
10. C. Paman, A. Kriza, V. Pop and S. Udrea, *J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 2005, **82**, 71.
11. M. Gielen, P. de Lelieveld, D. Vos and R. Wilen, "Metal Based Antitumour Drugs", Freund Publishing House, Belgium, 1992, **2**, 95.
12. H. Chojnacki, *J. Mol. Structure-Theochem.*, 2003, **630**, 291.
13. P. O. Dunstan, *Thermochimica Acta*, 2003, **398**, 1.
14. A. R. Morgan, G. M. Garbo, R. W. Keck and S. H. Selman, *Cancer Res.*, 1988, **48**, 194.
15. D. P. Arnold, B. A. Morrison and J. V. Hanna, *Polyhedron*, 1990, **9**, 1331; G. S. Drummond and A. Kappas, *J. Clin. Invest.*, 1989, **77**, 971.
16. G. D. Smith, V. M. Visciglio, P. E. Fenwick and I. P. Rothwell, *Organometallics*, 1992, **11**, 1064.
17. Konishi Teppe, *Nippon. Kaga. Koen. Yokoshy.*, 2005, **85**, 1094.
18. H. A. Szymaskii, "Interpretted Infrared Spectra", Plenum Press Data Division, New York, 1961, **3**, 7.
19. G. Socrates, "Infrared Characteristic Group Frequencies", John Wiley, New York, 1980, 46.
20. G. K. Sandhu and N. S. Boparoy, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1991, **411**, 89.
21. G. K. Sandhu, R. Gupta, S. S. Sandhu, R. V. Parish and K. Brown, *J. Organomet. Chem.*, 1985, **279**, 373.
22. G. R. Clark, A. J. Nielson and C. E. F. Rickard, *Polyhedron*, 1987, **6**, 1765.
23. H. J. Beristein, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **18**, 16; J. E. Stewart, *J. Chem. Phys.*, 1959, **30**, 1259; L. K. Dyllal and J. E. Kamp, *Spectrochim. Acta*, 1962, **16**, 1176.
24. N. S. Biradar and T. P. Gousser, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1977, **39**, 358.
25. K. J. Morgan, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1961, 2343; T. R. Harkins, J.

Note

- L. Walter, O. E. Harris and H. Freiser, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **78**, 260.
26. B. C. Curran, D. N. Sen, S. Mizyshima and J. Y. Quagliano, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1956, **76**, 429.
27. D. M. L. Goodgame, M. Goodgame, P. J. Hayward and G. W. Raymer-Canham, *Inorg. Chem.*, 1968, **7**, 2447; C. E. Taylor and A. E. Underhill, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1969, 368; B. Cornilsen and K. Nakamoto, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1974, **36**, 2467; G. A. Melson and R. H. Nuttall, *J. Mol. Struct.*, 1968, **01**, 405.
28. R. G. Inskoop, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1962, **24**, 763; A. S. Schilt and R. C. Taylor, *J. Inorg. Nucl. Chem.*, 1959, **9**, 211; K. C. Malhotra and Balkrishan, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1976, **14**, 869.
29. R. J. H. Clark, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1963, 1377; S. S. Shambov, *Z. Naturforsch*, 1969, **24**, 2015.
30. T. N. Srivastava and J. D. Singh, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1983, **22**, 128.
31. T. Sedaghat and S. Menati, *Inorg. Chem. Commun.*, 2004, **7**, 760.